

A Study on Comparative Analysis of Content Published on Disney+ and Amazon in Select Countries during 2015-2022

T. Surekha

Rishi UBR Women's College

Introduction

The entertainment industry has seen a great shift with the intervention of OTT administrators. Lifestyle and technology made life simple, easy yet more convenient. Movies and TV shows are entertaining audience at their homes. Global entertainment industry has drastically effected by the introduction of OTT platforms.

This study aims at comparative analysis of the two big players on global OTT platform-The Disney+ and Amazon.

Need of the Study

The purpose of the study to understand the descriptive analytics on genres, production _countries, runtime, type, release year, IMDb_Score and TMDb_Popularity of OTT platform Using advanced data and analytics (Power BI, Excel) Disney and Amazon is able to provide users with personalized movie and TV show recommendations. Analyzing the TMDb_Popularity and IMDb_Score with Runtime of select content, and specific years (2015-2022) before it predict marketing content such as trailers and thumbnail images to optimize production planning.

Objectives

1. To study the type of content and genres published by Disney+ and Amazon during 2015-2022.
2. To compare the IMDb_Score based content released during 2015-2022 in Disney+ and Amazon data.
3. To conduct the comparative analysis based on Runtime and Type of the content published on Disney+ and Amazon during 2015-2022.
4. To compare the content based on TMDb_Popularity in Disney+ and Amazon.

Scope of the Study

This study was to understand the comparative analysis of Disney+ and Amazon statistics for visualizing the select countries in select years. Specifically, the study sought to describe the top OTT platform by considering IMDb_Score, Runtime, Genres, TMDb_Popularity i.e., the most important factors in Disney+ and Amazon for rating the usage of the OTT platform. It says that the OTT services and users are scaled up when compared with beginning of the OTT platform, now anyone can benefit from the service and enjoy the platform with a limited budget.

Review of Literature

Rajat Kathuria (2019): India's OTT Market: Witnessing A Rise In Number Of Paid Subscribers.

The finding of the study says that the number of OTT players increased from just nine in 2012 to 32 in 2018. In 2017, the objective of the study is OTT industry in India achieved phenomenal growth of 160%. I considered it because the top 16 OTT platforms saw their user bases grow from 63 million to 164 million

between August 2016 and August 2017.

Gaikwad (2019): India is the world's fastest growing OTT market: PwC report.

The findings of the study says that the Growth for OTT is projected to be the fastest at a CAGR of 18.6% to \$1.73 billion by 2021, up from the estimated \$740 million in 2016, whereas for Internet video, the CAGR is higher at 22.4% albeit at a lower base of \$239 million it will continue through this we will assume that at such fast rate of development of technology.

Deloitte India (2019): Emergence and future of Over-the-top OTT video services in India: an analytical research.

That the television and appointment viewing will continue for an additional ten years. The rationale is that televisions are now extremely affordable, and other people can get a basic cable connection for Rs. 120 a month. The study's finding tells that Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala and Andhra Pradesh have over 90% of television penetration after the implementation of OTT platforms.

ET Brand Equity (2019): 55% of Indians prefer OTT platforms vs 41% that still prefer DTH: Mo MAGIC survey.

The objective of the study says that OTT is that the way ahead with mobile becoming the –be it all, however brands and marketers cannot discount the DTH. With quite 40% still preferring DTH, it's still an extended thanks to connect with the opposite India which is what presents a chance and marketplace for companies to tap on. Going ahead, we expect OTT to grab additional share but DTH will still remain relevant. The study says that there will be segmentation going forward; generation familiar with DTH will continue thereupon where because the generation Z is going to be aligned to OTT.

Quresh Moochhala (2019): The Future of Online OTT Entertainment Services in India.

The study says that the number of Internet-connected TV devices has grown significantly in recent years, especially Over-the-Top (OTT) streaming devices. OTT devices offer an alternate to multi- channel television subscription services, and are often monetized through behavioral advertising. The objective is to shed light on the privacy practices of such platforms, we developed a system which will automatically download OTT apps (also referred to as channels), and interact with them while intercepting the network traffic and performing best-effort TLS interception. We used this smart crawler to go to quite 2,000 channels on two popular OTT platforms, namely Netflix and Amazon prime TV. The conclusion of their results show that tracking is pervasive on both OTT platforms, with traffic to known trackers present on 69% of Amazon channels and 89% of Netflix TV channels.

Research Methodology

Source of Data

This study is based on secondary data. Data is collected from a public source through internet (www.kaggle.com). This dataset consists of details on TV Shows and Movies published on Amazon and Disney+ during 2015-2022 (January).

Sample Size

The study was conducted by taking a sample duration with 2015-2022 (January) in select countries - United States, United Kingdom, Japan, India, Australia, Spain, China, Germany, Canada, Italy, France, Netherlands, Korea Republic.

Data Analysis Tools and Techniques

Power BI Excel.

Theoretical Framework

Business analytics is the process by which businesses use statistical methods and technologies based on historical data in order to attain organizational goals and make profit.

Business Analyst

The key role a business analyst plays when conducting an analysis of a business is requirements management. The modern business environment is complex and the business analyst's role is to maintain requirements through constant change by using innovation to do so.

Descriptive Analysis

Is the type of analysis of data that helps describe, show or summarize data points in a constructive way such that patterns might emerge that fulfill every condition of the data. It is one of the most important steps for conducting statistical data analysis.

How Is Descriptive Analytics Used?

Companies use descriptive analytics across many parts of the business to evaluate how well they are operating and whether they're on track to attain business goals. Business leaders and financial specialists track common financial metrics produced by descriptive analytics, such as quarterly growth in revenue and expenses. Marketing teams use descriptive analytics to track campaign performance by monitoring metrics like conversion rates and the number of social media followers. Manufacturing groups monitor metrics such as production line throughput and downtime.

The metrics produced by descriptive analytics are used in various ways, including:

- **Reports:** The key financial metrics included in a company's financial statements are generated by descriptive analytics. Other common reports also use descriptive analytics to highlight aspects of business performance.
- **Visualizations:** Displaying metrics in charts and other graphic representations can more efficiently communicate their impact to a wider audience.
- **Dashboards:** Executives, managers and other employees may use dashboards to track progress and manage their daily workload. Dashboards present a selection of KPIs and other important information tailored to the needs of each person. The information may be represented as charts or other visualizations to enable people to absorb it more quickly.

Inference 1:

Analysis Based On Genres Of Content Produced In Select Countries Published On Disney+ During 2015-2022

Chart 6.1: Count of genres by production_countries (Disney+)

Interpretation

It is observed from the above table and graph that majority of the genres (123) were adopted to create content in United States (US), second and third countries that made content in next highest genres are United kingdom (GB) (37), and Japan (32). Other select countries India, Australia, Spain, China, Germany, Canada, Italy, France, Netherlands, Korea, Republic (KR) produced content in less than 10 genres (7 to 1)

Inference 2

Analysis Based On Genres And Production Countries On The Content Published On Amazon During 2015-2022 In Select Countries.

Chart 6.2: Count of genres by production_countries (Amazon)

Interpretation

It is observed from the above table and graph that majority of the genres (157) were adopted to create

content in United States (US), second and third countries that made content in next highest genres are India (66), United Kingdom (31) and other select countries Japan, Australia, Spain, China, Germany, Canada, Italy, France, Netherlands, Korea Republic (KR) produced content in less than 30 genres (29 to 3).

Inference 3

Comparative Analysis On Genres Based Content Produced In Select Countries On Disney+ and Amazon.

Chart 6.3: Genres of Content Produced on Disney+ and Amazon

Interpretation

It is observed from the above table and graph that the highest genre of content is produced in United state when compared with India, United Kingdom, Japan, China, Canada, France, Australia, Germany, Spain, Italy and Netherlands.

Inference 4

Comparative Analysis Based On Runtime For Movies And TV Shows Produced On Disney+ And Amazon Published During 2015-2022 In Select Countries.

Chart 6.4: Runtime by Type

Interpretation

It is observed from the above table and graph that the Amazon secured 91% in movies and 8.8% in TV shows in runtime, Disney+ secured 50% in movies and 50% in TV shows respective years.

Inference 5

Analysis Based On Release Year And IMDb_Score On The Content Published On Disney+ During 2015-2022.

Chart 6.5: IMDb Score by Release year (Disney+)

Interpretation

It is observed that from the above table and graph the highest release year is 2017 with 16.93% and the least year is 2022 with 4.25% and remaining with 2015 (15.50%), 2016 (12.44%), 2018 (13.30%), 2019

(15.33%), 2020 (11.03%), 2021 (11.23%).

Inference 6

Analysis Based On IMDb_Score For The Content Published On Amazon During 2015-2022.

Chart 6.6: IMDb Score by Release year (Amazon)

Interpretation

It is observed from the above table and graph that the highest release year is 2018 with 16.94% and the least release year is 2022 with 4.23% Other years were 2015 (16.30%), 2016 (12.44%), 2017 (15.50%), 2019 (15.33%), 2020 (11.03%), 2021 (11.23%).

Inference 7

Comparative Analysis Of IMDb_Score Based On Release Year On Disney+ And Amazon Published During 2015-2022.

Chart 6.7: IMDb Score (Disney+ and Amazon) by Release year

Interpretation

It is observed that from the table and graph that the Amazon secured highest in IMDb_Score with 526 (16.94%) when compared Disney+ IMDb_Score with 286 (15.33%).

Inference 8

Analysis Based On TMDb_Popularity And Release Year On Disney+.

Interpretation

It is observed that from the above table and graph the TMDb_Popularity is highest in the 2015 (18.65%) and the least in the 2016 (6.70%) Neutral in the 2021 with 17.76% and remaining are with 56.89%.

Inference 9

Analysis Based On TMDb_Popularity And Release Year On Amazon Of 2015-2022.

Interpretation

It is observed that from the above table and graph the TMDb_Popularity is highest in the 2021 (29.86%) the least in the 2015 (6.70%) and remaining are with

Inference 10

Comparative Analysis Of TMDb_Popularity Based On Disney+ And Amazon Published During 2015-2022.

Interpretation

It is observed that from the above table and graph that the Amazon TMDb_Popularity secured highest than Disney+ TMDb_Popularity, excluding the year 2015.

Research Findings and Conclusion

1. Majority of the genres (123) were adopted to create content in United States (US) in Disney.
2. Majority of the genres (157) were adopted to create content in United States (US) in Amazon.
3. As compared to Disney movies and TV shows, Amazon Runtime is high in movies with 91% and TV shows with 8.8%.
4. The highest release year is 2017 with 16.93% and the least year is 2022 with 4.25%.
5. As Amazon secured highest in IMDb_Score with 526 (16.94%).
6. As compared to Disney IMDb_Score, Amazon secured highest in IMDb_Score with 526 (16.94%).
7. As compared with Amazon, TMDb_Popularity secured highest than Disney TMDb_Popularity, excluding the year 2015.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis of the Disney and Amazon OTT platforms in select countries, has led to find out the favourite and most used OTT platform out of Disney+ and Amazon. This study helped us to identify the high genre of content produced, runtime based on type (movies and TV shows), IMDb_Score on selected countries with specific release years (2015-2022) as follows with TMDb_Popularity and various factors

influencing people to opt their favourite OTT platforms.

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